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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ikki o'zgaruvchili gipergeometrik funksiyalarning elementar funksiyalarda ifodalash usullari tatbiq qilish

Абстрактный: В статье применяются методы выражения гипергеометрических функций двух переменных в элементарных функциях

Abstract: In this article, methods of expression of two-variable hypergeometric functions in elementary functions are applied.

The generalized hypergeometric function ${}_qF_p$ is a power series in which the ratio of successive terms is a rational function of the summation index. The Gaussian hypergeometric functions ${}_2F_1$ and ${}_3F_2$ are most common special cases of the generalized hypergeometric function ${}_qF_p$. The Appell hypergeometric functions F_1, F_2, F_3 and F_4 are product of two hypergeometric functions ${}_2F_1$ that appear in many areas of mathematical physics. Here, we are interested in the Appell hypergeometric function F_2 which is known to have a double integral representation. As demonstrated by Opps, Saad and Srivastava [1], the double integral representation of F_2 can be reduced to a single integral that can be easily evaluated for certain values of the parameters in terms of ${}_2F_1$ and ${}_3F_2$. Using many of the reduction formulas of ${}_2F_1$ and ${}_3F_2$ and the representation of F_2 in terms of a single integral, we have begun to tabulate new reduction formulas for F_2 .

The Appell hypergeometric functions F_1, F_2, F_3 and F_4 play an important role in mathematical physics. In particular, the Appell hypergeometric series F_2 arises frequently in various physical and chemical applications. The exact solution of number of problems in quantum mechanics has been given in terms of Appell's function F_2 . It is defined by

$$F_2(\sigma, \alpha_1, \alpha_2; \beta_1, \beta_2; x, y) = \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\sigma)_{m+n} (\alpha_1)_m (\alpha_2)_n}{(\beta_1)_m (\beta_2)_n} \frac{x^m y^n}{m! n!}, \quad (1)$$

for $|x|+|y|<1$; $\beta_j \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$; $\mathbb{N}^- := \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}$, and $(\lambda)_k$ denoted the Pochhammer symbol defined, in terms of Gamma functions, by

$$(\lambda)_k := \frac{\Gamma(\lambda+k)}{\Gamma(\lambda)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (k=0; \lambda \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}) \\ \lambda(\lambda+1)(\lambda+2)\dots(\lambda+k-1) & \text{if } (k \in \mathbb{N}; \lambda \in \mathbb{N}) \end{cases}$$

where $\mathbb{N}$ being the set of positive integers. Further, it also has the following double integral representation [2]:

$$F_2(\sigma, \alpha_1, \alpha_2; \beta_1, \beta_2; x, y) = \frac{\Gamma(\beta_1)\Gamma(\beta_2)}{\Gamma(\alpha_1)\Gamma(\alpha_2)\Gamma(\beta_1 - \alpha_1)\Gamma(\beta_2 - \alpha_2)} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 u^{\alpha_1-1} r^{\alpha_2-1} \times (2) \\ \times (1-u)^{\beta_1-\alpha_1-1} (1-r)^{\beta_2-\alpha_2-1} (1-xu-yr)^{-\sigma} dudr$$

where $\text{Re}(\beta_j) > \text{Re}(\alpha_j) > 0, j=1,2$ and $|x|+|y| < 1$. Recently, Opps et al. [1] used the Euler's integral representation of the Gauss hypergeometric function [2] to reduce the double integral representation (2) into a single integral in term of ${}_2F_1$. Using some properties of ${}_2F_1$, they prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1. For $|x|+|y| < 1$, the Appell hypergeometric function F_2 is given by

$$F_2(a+1, \alpha_1, 1; \beta_1, 2; x, y) = -\frac{1}{ay} {}_2F_1\left(\begin{matrix} a, \alpha_1 \\ \beta_1 \end{matrix}; x\right) + \frac{1}{ay(1-y)^a} {}_2F_1\left(\begin{matrix} a, \alpha_1 \\ \beta_1 \end{matrix}; \frac{x}{1-y}\right)$$

where $a \neq 0; \alpha_1 \in \mathbb{C}; \beta_1 \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-$ and

$$F_2(1, \alpha_1, 1; \beta_1, 2; x, y) = \frac{\alpha_1}{\beta_1 y} \left[\frac{x}{1-y} {}_3F_2\left(\begin{matrix} \alpha_1+1, 1, 1 \\ \beta_1+1, 2 \end{matrix}; \frac{x}{1-y}\right) - x {}_3F_2\left(\begin{matrix} \alpha_1+1, 1, 1 \\ \beta_1+1, 2 \end{matrix}; x\right) \right] - \frac{\ln(1-y)}{y}$$

where $\alpha_1 \in \mathbb{C}; \beta_1 \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-$.

Using the Theorem1, we find special values of the Appell hypergeometric function F_2 . For example,

1. $F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, 1; -\frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} [\sqrt{1-x} - \sqrt{1-x-y}]$.
2. $F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} [\sqrt{1-x} - \sqrt{1-x-y} + \sqrt{x} (\arcsin \sqrt{x} - \arcsin \sqrt{x/(1-y)})]$.
3. $F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2}, 1; \frac{3}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{3y} \left[\frac{3-4x}{\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{3-3y-4x}{\sqrt{1-x-y}} \right]$.
4. $F_2(2, 1, 1; 2, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{xy} \ln \frac{(1-x)(1-y)}{1-x-y}$.
5. $F_2(5, 4, 1; 3, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{12y} \left[\frac{2-3y+x}{(1-x-y)^5} - \frac{3+x}{(1-x)^2} \right]$.
6. $F_2(5, 3, 1; 2, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{4y} \left[\frac{1-y+x}{(1-x-y)^5} - \frac{1+x}{(1-x)^2} \right]$.
7. $F_2\left(\frac{9}{2}, \frac{7}{2}, 1; \frac{7}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{7y} [\sqrt{(1-x-y)^7} - \sqrt{(1-x)^7}]$.
8. $F_2(1, 2, 1; 1, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{y} \left[\frac{xy}{(1-x)(1-x-y)} + \ln \frac{(1-x)}{1-x-y} \right]$.
9. $F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} \left[\frac{1-2x}{\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{1-y-2x}{\sqrt{1-y-x}} \right]$
10. $F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}; 1, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1-y} - \sqrt{x} \left(\tanh^{-1} \sqrt{x} - \tanh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{x}{1-y}} \right) \right]$
11. $F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}; 4, 1; 3, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{1}{3y} \left[\frac{6-7x}{\sqrt{1-x}} - \frac{6-6y-7x}{\sqrt{1-y-x}} \right]$

$$12. F_2\left(1; -\frac{1}{2}, 1; 1, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} \left[\sqrt{\frac{1-x-y}{1-y}} - \sqrt{1-x} + \ln\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1-y}+\sqrt{1-x-y}}\right) \right]$$

$$13. F_2\left(1; \frac{1}{2}, 1; 1, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} \ln\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{1-x}}{\sqrt{1-y}+\sqrt{1-x-y}}\right)$$

$$14. F_2(1; 1, 1; 2, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{xy} \left[(1-x-y) \ln(1-x-y) - (1-y) \ln(1-y) - (1-x) \ln(1-x) \right]$$

$$15. F_2\left(1; \frac{3}{2}, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{1}{y} \left[\frac{2xy}{(1-x)(1-x-y)} + \ln\left(\frac{1-x}{1-x-y}\right) \right]$$

$$16. F_2\left(1; \frac{3}{2}, 1; -\frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{1}{y} \left[\frac{4xy(x^2+y-1)5-6x}{(1-x)^2(1-x-y)^2} + \ln\left(\frac{1-x}{1-x-y}\right) \right]$$

$$17. F_2\left(\frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{4}, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{y} \left[\frac{\sqrt{\sqrt{1-y}+\sqrt{1-x-y}}}{\sqrt{1-x-y}} - \frac{\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1-x}}}{\sqrt{1-x}} \right]$$

$$18. F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}; 1, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1-y} - \sqrt{x} \left(\tanh^{-1} \sqrt{x} - \tanh^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{x}{1-y}} \right) \right]$$

$$19. F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}; \frac{5}{2}, 1; \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{2}{3y} \left[\frac{3-12x+8x^2}{(1-x)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - \frac{3(1-y)^2-12x(1-y)+8x^2}{(1-y-x)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right]$$

$$20. F_2(5; 4, 1; 3, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{12y} \left[\frac{3(1-y)^2+x}{(1-x-y)^5} + \frac{3+x}{(1-x)^5} \right]$$

$$21. F_2\left(5; \frac{7}{2}, 1; 3, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{5}{2y} \left[\frac{6(1-y)+x}{\sqrt{1-y}(1-x-y)^{\frac{9}{2}}} - \frac{6+x}{(1-x)^{\frac{9}{2}}} \right]$$

$$22. F_2\left(5; \frac{5}{2}, 1, 3, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{1}{24y} \left[\frac{6(1-y)-x}{(1-y)^{\frac{3}{2}}(1-x-y)^{\frac{7}{2}}} - \frac{6-x}{(1-x)^{\frac{7}{2}}} \right]$$

$$23. F_2\left(5; \frac{3}{2}, 1, \frac{1}{2}, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{1}{4y} \left[\frac{1-y+7x}{(1-x-y)^5} - \frac{1+7x}{(1-x)^5} \right]$$

$$24. F_2\left(4; \frac{7}{2}, 1; 2, 2; x, y\right) = \frac{1}{12y} \left[\frac{\sqrt{1-y}(4(1-y)+3x)}{(1-x-y)^{\frac{9}{2}}} - \frac{4+3x}{(1-x)^{\frac{9}{2}}} \right]$$

$$25. F_2(3; 4, 1; 1, 2; x, y) = \frac{1}{2y} \left[\frac{(1-y)^2(1-y+3x)}{(1-x-y)^5} - \frac{1+3x}{(1-x)^5} \right]$$

The process can be continued.

References

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